

PROBLEMS OF ARCHITECTURE AND CONSTRUCTION

Scientific and technical journal

e-ISSN: 2901-7845 (ISSN: 2091-5004)

2026, VOLUME-04, ISSUE-02.

The journal is included in the list of scientific journals in which scientific articles on technical sciences (construction, mechanics and machine building) and architecture are subject to publication by the decision of the OAK Board (certificate No. 00757. 2000.31.01). It is hereby notified that the articles published in English in our journal are equated to scientific articles published in foreign scientific publications in accordance with the decision of the OAK

Google Scholar provides a simple way to broadly search for scholarly literature.

Any status is accepted, from any stage of the research lifecycle

Wikipedia is a free online encyclopedia created by volunteers around the world

Open Journal Systems (OJS) is an open source solution to managing and publishing scholarly journals online.

journal link

International
Standard
Serial
Number
International
centre

HISTORICAL AND URBAN PLANNING TRANSFORMATION OF TASHKENT'S RESIDENTIAL FABRIC: FROM MAHALLA STRUCTURE TO CONTEMPORARY DENSIFICATION

Oydin Shoumarova Abbos qizi¹

¹PhD Candidate, Tashkent University of Architecture and Civil Engineering, Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan

Abstract. This article examines the historical and urban planning transformation of Tashkent's residential fabric in relation to contemporary densification. Based on historical-urban and morphological analysis, it identifies the main stages in the formation of the city's residential environment: the traditional mahalla, the colonial dual structure of the Old and New City, the Soviet microdistrict, infill development during the independence period, and contemporary high-rise complexes. The study shows that Tashkent's residential fabric developed through the overlapping of historical layers with different planning structures, building heights, block scales, and open-space patterns. The article argues that densification should be assessed through a differentiated approach that considers the historically formed morphology of the urban fabric and the balance between built-up and open spaces.

Keywords: residential development, urban fabric, historical and urban planning development, mahalla, microdistrict, residential densification, urban morphology, open spaces, quality of the urban environment.

Introduction. Tashkent's contemporary residential fabric was formed through the overlapping of several historical stages: the traditional mahalla, the regular structure of the colonial period, Soviet microdistricts, infill development during the independence period, and contemporary high-rise residential complexes. These layers created a heterogeneous urban environment that differs in block scale, building height, open-space patterns, and spatial connectivity.

The transition from low-rise courtyard-based mahalla fabric to the large-scale microdistrict model of the Soviet period is particularly important for understanding Tashkent's contemporary structure. Traditional development was based on internal courtyards, narrow streets, and aryk irrigation channels [1], [2], while Soviet reconstruction introduced major roads, standardized multi-storey housing, and open intra-block spaces [3].

In contemporary conditions, densification affects these historically formed types of residential fabric in different ways. Therefore, this article aims to identify the main stages of the historical and urban planning transformation of Tashkent's residential development and to show their significance for understanding contemporary densification.

Research methodology. The study is based on historical-urban and morphological analysis of Tashkent's residential fabric. The materials include scholarly publications on Tashkent's urban development, the traditional mahalla structure, Soviet reconstruction, and contemporary residential transformation [1]–[8]. The theoretical basis is also supported by previous research on the evolution of urban density concepts and their influence on the urban environment [9]. In addition, the study relies on earlier Spacematrix-based research on urban form typology and density indicators in

Tashkent, which identified relationships between urban morphology, density, and open-space structure [10].

The methodology involves a sequential examination of the main stages in the formation of Tashkent's residential fabric: the pre-colonial city, the colonial period, the Soviet stage, the independence period, and the contemporary stage of intensive densification. For each stage, the analysis focuses on the type of residential development, planning structure, block scale,

building height, open-space patterns, and the degree of connectivity of the urban fabric.

Particular attention is paid to four morphological manifestations of the residential environment: traditional mahalla development, the Soviet microdistrict, infill development during the independence period, and contemporary high-rise residential development. This approach makes it possible to interpret Tashkent's historical development as a process that shaped the city's current heterogeneous structure.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the territorial growth of Tashkent from the 19th century to 2025

1. Pre-colonial Period: The Mahalla Structure of Tashkent. Before the colonial transformation of the city in the second half of the nineteenth century, Tashkent developed as a traditional oasis city, whose spatial structure was closely related to climatic conditions, the irrigation system, and the neighbourhood-based organization of the residential environment [1], [2]. The urban fabric was primarily formed by mahallas - local residential units characterized by low-rise courtyard housing, internal courtyards, narrow streets, cul-de-sacs, and a network of aryk irrigation channels.

By 1865, the population of Tashkent was about 80,000 people, while the area within the city walls was approximately 1,600 hectares [4]. Thus, the average population density of the old city may be estimated at about 50 people per hectare. This indicates that the pre-colonial residential environment was not highly dense in demographic terms; however, it had a compact

morphology: houses were located close to one another, forming a dense carpet-like fabric with narrow passages and internal courtyards.

This structure combined built-up areas with open spaces within individual plots. Houses were generally oriented inward toward courtyards, which ensured privacy, climatic protection, and courtyard-garden organization. Courtyards, gardens, aryk channels, and the suburban green zone of mauza supported the city's oasis character.

Thus, pre-colonial Tashkent demonstrates a specific type of density: low-rise and moderate in demographic terms, but horizontally compact in morphology. This shows that density depends not only on building height, but also on the relationship between built form, courtyards, streets, and greenery.

2. Colonial Period: The Formation of the Dual Structure of the Old and New City. After Tashkent was incorporated into the Russian

Empire in 1865, the city acquired a dual structure. Alongside the historical Old City, which preserved the mahalla fabric, a New City began to develop to the east for administrative, military, and residential functions [1]. Unlike the organic layout of the old city, the New City was based on a regular block grid, straight streets, public spaces, and engineering infrastructure.

This contrast strengthened the spatial difference between two types of urban fabric. The Old City retained low-rise courtyard housing, narrow streets, cul-de-sacs, aryk channels, and internal courtyards. The New City formed a more open and regular structure with wider streets, green spaces, and larger blocks. By the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, this duality had become one of the first sources of Tashkent's morphological heterogeneity.

The growth of the city's administrative importance was accompanied by an increase in both population and territory. While in 1865 about 80,000 people lived within the Old City, which covered approximately 1,600 hectares, by 1917 the population had reached around 280,000–300,000 people, and the city area had expanded to about 33 km² [11]. Accordingly, the average population density may have increased from about 50 people per hectare to approximately 85–90 people per hectare. However, this growth did not produce a unified urban structure: density was distributed unevenly between the Old City, the New City, and the developing peripheral areas.

Thus, the colonial period laid the foundation for Tashkent's spatial duality, where the compact mahalla fabric of the Old City began to coexist with the regular block structure of the New City. This contrast became one of the earliest sources of the city's later morphological heterogeneity.

3. Soviet Stage: The Microdistrict Model and the Reconstruction of the Urban Fabric.

The Soviet period became a key stage in the spatial transformation of Tashkent. After the city received the status of the capital of the Uzbek SSR, it began to develop actively as an administrative, industrial, and cultural centre. This was accompanied by population growth, territorial expansion, the development of engineering and transport infrastructure, and a transition to mass housing construction [6].

Particularly significant changes took place after the 1966 earthquake, when the reconstruction of Tashkent became the basis for the formation of a new planning structure. During this period, the construction of standardized residential buildings, large housing estates, and microdistricts intensified. In contrast to the traditional mahalla fabric, the microdistrict model was based on enlarged blocks, the free placement of buildings, the inclusion of schools, kindergartens, service facilities, and open intra-block spaces [3],[7].

The size of microdistricts significantly exceeded the scale of traditional quarters and often reached 20–30 hectares or more. Population density in such residential formations increased to 300–400 people per hectare, and in some areas to 500–600 people per hectare [4]. At the same time, a higher level of residential provision was achieved not only through increased building height, but also through the standardization of the residential environment, centralized utilities, and the placement of social infrastructure within residential areas.

In the 1970s–1980s, the main zones of mass housing construction included Chilanzar, Sergeli, Yunusabad, Karasu, Kuyluk, and other districts [7]. Residential development of this period was represented mainly by standardized multi-storey buildings organized within the microdistrict system. By 1983, the population of Tashkent had reached approximately 1.9 million people, while the city area was about 256 km²

[5]. The development of the metro system from 1977 further strengthened the city's transport connectivity and consolidated the new large-scale structure of the urban environment [12].

Thus, the Soviet stage formed a major layer of Tashkent's residential fabric: microdistrict and multi-storey housing development. It increased residential density and social infrastructure provision, but also changed the scale of the urban fabric and weakened fine-grained spatial connectivity. Today, these areas often become sites of conflict between additional construction and the preservation of open spaces.

4. Independence Period: Fragmented Development and New Forms of Densification.

After 1991, the urban development of Tashkent changed: instead of the large centralized programmes of the Soviet period, market mechanisms, private construction, and local transformations of the residential environment became more prominent. In the 1990s, the city's population stabilized at around 2.1–2.2 million people; however, from the 2000s, growth resumed, and by 2016 the population had reached approximately 2.5 million [13].

This period combined two divergent processes: peripheral expansion and infill densification of the existing urban fabric. New individual and low-rise housing developed on the outskirts, while central and inner-city districts saw commercial facilities, multi-storey housing, and local redevelopment. As a result, density became increasingly uneven.

The independence period also affected historical mahalla areas. Despite the preservation of individual monuments and ensembles, the everyday residential fabric of the Old City gradually lost integrity, as historical quarters were often treated as reserves for new construction. Thus, the independence period intensified the fragmentation of Tashkent's residential fabric through peripheral expansion,

infill development, commercialization, increased motorization, and partial loss of historical fabric.

5. Contemporary Stage: Intensive Densification and Transformation of the Residential Environment.

The contemporary stage of Tashkent's development is characterized by a shift from the fragmented transformation of the independence period toward more intensive use of urban territories. Densification is manifested in the construction of high-rise residential complexes, the redevelopment of individual plots within the existing urban fabric, the emergence of large multifunctional projects, and the increasing pressure on transport and social infrastructure.

The most noticeable changes are taking place in the central and inner-city districts, where available land is limited and the demand for housing and commercial functions remains high. Under these conditions, new development is increasingly being inserted into the already formed urban fabric. This leads to changes in the scale of the environment, an increase in building height, and a transformation in the relationship between built-up and open spaces.

Large projects such as Tashkent City and Business City reflect the transition toward a more intensive and multifunctional model of urban development, strengthening the contrast between historical residential fabric and contemporary high-density complexes. The renewal of the city's transport structure is another important direction of development. Materials related to the General Plan of Tashkent until 2045 emphasize the need to increase the role of public transport, expand the metro system, and introduce new types of urban mobility [14]. Under densification, this is essential for maintaining the quality of the urban environment.

Thus, the contemporary stage forms a new layer of Tashkent's residential fabric: high-

intensity multi-storey and multifunctional development. Unlike the mahalla structure and the Soviet microdistrict, it is associated with vertical growth, a high concentration of functions, and increased pressure on urban territory. This makes the balance between housing growth, open spaces, pedestrian connectivity, greenery, and infrastructure particularly important.

Discussion. The historical development of Tashkent shows that its contemporary residential fabric was formed through the overlapping of different urban planning layers rather than through the replacement of one

type of development by another. Each layer has its own spatial logic, block scale, open-space structure, and sensitivity to densification.

The mahalla structure represents compact low-rise fabric, where density is primarily associated with horizontal organization, internal courtyards, narrow streets, and local connections. The Soviet microdistrict is based on enlarged blocks, free-standing buildings, open intra-block spaces, and social infrastructure. Contemporary high-rise development forms another type of density, associated with vertical growth, functional concentration, and increased pressure on transport and social infrastructure.

Fig. 2. Historical layers in the formation of Tashkent's residential fabric

This distinction is essential for assessing contemporary densification. In mahalla areas, additional construction may disrupt courtyard organization, local connectivity, and historical scale. In Soviet microdistricts, densification often affects intra-block open spaces. In contemporary high-rise districts, the key issue is the balance between density, transport accessibility, greenery, public spaces, and services.

Thus, densification in Tashkent cannot be regulated through a single approach for all territories. Taking historical layers into account

makes it possible to move from a purely quantitative understanding of density to a more comprehensive approach that includes urban morphology, open spaces, infrastructure, and environmental quality.

Conclusion. The historical and urban planning analysis showed that Tashkent's contemporary residential fabric was formed through the overlapping of several stages: the traditional mahalla structure, the regular planning of the colonial period, the Soviet microdistrict model, transformations of the independence period, and contemporary

intensive densification. Each stage produced a specific type of residential environment, differing in block scale, building height, open-space patterns, and spatial connectivity.

The study found that mahalla development represents horizontal compactness with low building height; the Soviet microdistrict represents a large-scale residential model with intra-block open spaces; and contemporary high-rise development represents vertical density and increased pressure on urban territory. The independence period intensified fragmentation through local densification, peripheral expansion, and point transformations of the existing fabric.

Contemporary densification in Tashkent should therefore be assessed in a differentiated way. For mahalla areas, the preservation of scale and courtyard structure is essential; for Soviet microdistricts, the protection of open spaces is important; and for new high-rise districts, infrastructural balance, greenery, pedestrian accessibility, and the quality of public spaces are required.

References:

1. Nielsen, V. A. *At the Origins of Modern Urban Planning in Uzbekistan: The Nineteenth and Early Twentieth Centuries*. Tashkent: Gafur Gulyam Publishing House of Literature and Art, 1988. [in Russian]
2. Yaralov, Yu. S., ed. *General History of Architecture in 12 Volumes. Vol. 8: Architecture of the Mediterranean Countries, Africa and Asia from the Sixth to the Nineteenth Centuries*. Moscow, 1969. [in Russian]
3. Stronski, P. M. *Tashkent: Forging a Soviet City, 1930–1966*. Pittsburgh: University of Pittsburgh Press, 2010.
4. Banke, A. I., Puretsky, Yu. P., et al. *General Plan for the Development of Tashkent*. Tashkent, 1967. [in Russian]

5. Askarov, Sh. D. *Architecture of Uzbekistan and the CIS Countries*. Tashkent: San'at Publishing House, 2012. [in Russian]

6. Askarov, Sh. D. *Genesis of the Architecture of Uzbekistan*. Tashkent, 2014. [in Russian]

7. Akhmedov, M. K., Nazarova, D. A., and Khasanov, A. O. *Development Paths of Architecture and Urban Planning in Uzbekistan*. Tashkent: Fan va texnologiya, 2016. [in Uzbek]

8. Chukhovich, B. L., and Kazakova, O. V. *Tashkent: Architecture of Soviet Modernism, 1955–1991: Guidebook*. Moscow: Garage Museum of Contemporary Art, 2025. ISBN 978-5-605-17168-3. [in Russian]

9. Shoumarova, O. A., and Vetlugina, A. V. "Evolution of Urban Density Concepts and Their Influence on the Urban Environment." *Construction and Education*, no. 5, 2025. Available online: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/evolution-of-urban-density-concepts-and-their-influence-on-the-urban-environment> (accessed 18 May 2026).

10. Shoumarova, O. A., Vetlugina, A. V., and Norboeva, M. A. "Typology of Urban Form and Density Indicators: Application of the Spacematrix Method to the Districts of Tashkent." *Universum: Technical Sciences*, no. 6(135), 2025. Available online: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tipologiya-gorodskoy-formy-i-pokazateli-plotnosti-primeneniye-metodiki-spacematrix-na-primere-rayonov-tashkenta> (accessed 18 May 2026).

11. Gusterin, P. V. *Tashkent: City, History and Modernity*. Available online: <https://www.booksite.ru/fulltext/1/001/008/109/256.htm>. Accessed 30 June 2025. [in Russian]

12. Makhmudova, M. "Interior Design of Tashkent Metro: Features of Its Architecture and Construction." *Society. Integration. Education: Proceedings of the International Scientific*

Conference, vol. 4, 2019, pp. 440–451.
<https://doi.org/10.17770/sie2019vol4.3887>.

13. National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Permanent Population by Regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Available online: <https://stat.uz/> (accessed 30 June 2025).

14. Gazeta.uz. *“Detailed Analysis of the Draft General Plan of Tashkent until 2045.”* Published 25 October 2022. Available online: <https://www.gazeta.uz/ru/2022/10/25/master-plan/>. Accessed 17 July 2025. [in Russian]

